

COMPARISON OF LITERATURE CURRICULA IN FINLAND AND UZBEKISTAN IN THE LIGHT OF WIDER EDUCATIONAL CONTEXTS

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Abstract. *Reading literacy is seen as one of the key determinants of both students' academic success and success in life outside school. With literature being one of the main subjects in school curriculum that aims to develop reading literacy, different education systems adopt different approaches to teaching literature. The article compares approaches to literature education in Finland and Uzbekistan in the light of their wider educational contexts, and argues that Uzbekistan needs to reconsider its current practices if policy goals to raise education standards are to be achieved.*

Keywords: *literature curriculum, teaching literature, reading literacy, PISA, PIRLS, Uzbekistan, Finland.*

Introduction

Reading literacy – ability to retrieve information from texts, understand their explicit and implicit ideas, interpret, respond to and evaluate them affects both academic success in school environment and success in broader life. Literature as a school subject that provides an opportunity to engage with texts created by different authors for different audiences in different historical, social and cultural contexts plays an important role not only in developing students' reading literacy, but also in bringing up generations of critical thinkers, creative problem-solvers and empathetic members of society.

Analysing approaches to teaching literature within the school curriculum, two distinct approaches can be identified. One approach is teaching literature as part of language: literature is not identified as a separate subject, but rather literature-related competences are considered as part of language competences and developed within the language classes. Finland and Canada, both among top performers in international studies of student achievements such as PISA and PIRLS, can be brought as examples of systems that follow this approach. On other hand, some other systems make a distinction between language and literature classes, each having their own goals, learning objectives, content and assessment schemes. Under this approach, literature as a subject is usually introduced when students transfer to middle or high school. Singapore, another top country in international PIRLS and PISA rankings, can be an example of this approach. Most post-soviet education systems, including Uzbekistan, also follow this approach. In the following paragraphs, approaches to literature education in Finland and Uzbekistan are compared in more detail considering their more general educational contexts. This comparison not only reveals the major differences in goals and approaches to teaching literature within the school curriculum, but also can suggest wider implications of these differences to students' overall academic performance.

Case of Finland: A holistic approach to developing reading literacy

Finland has been one of the most spoken about nations in education, given the outstanding performance of its students in the first iterations of PISA – a worldwide study by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) of 15-year-old students’ mathematics, science, and reading skills (or literacies, as they are called in the study). In 2000, Finnish students performed significantly higher than any other participating country: the study revealed that their information retrieval and text interpretation skills were highly developed, with reflection and evaluation skills not as strong but still not significantly lower than other top countries in PISA (Väljärvi, V. et al, 2002). Even though the results have declined since then, Finland still remains among the most successful systems. Authors attribute its success to several factors related both to the features of education system and the overall social, economic and cultural peculiarities of Finland as a nation, such as comprehensive school system that strives to provide equal access to quality education, strong teacher training system, school autonomy, and school curriculum that promotes interest in and engagement with reading (OECD, 2001; Väljärvi et al, 2002; Hamme et al, 2014). Also, important factors contributing to the successful performance of education system are focus on literacy skills rather than knowledge transmission, close match between curricular demands and teaching practices, and holistic approach to the curriculum reform with stakeholders convinced of and committed to the goals of a new curriculum (Ustun and Eyrilmaz, 2018; Pietarinen et al, 2017).

According to Finland’s Basic Education Act, the purpose of education is “to support pupils’ growth into humanity and into ethically responsible membership of society and to provide them with knowledge and skills needed in life” as well as “to promote civilisation and equality in society” (Basic Education Act, 1998). In line with these broader goals of education, National Core Curriculum for Basic Education identifies seven transversal competences (thinking and learning to learn; cultural competence, interaction and self-expression; taking care of oneself and managing daily life; multiliteracy; ICT competence; working life and entrepreneurship; participation, involvement and building a sustainable future) which schools should aim to promote by providing students with an interactive and engaging environment (Finnish National Board of Education, 2016). These competences also affect what subject-specific competences are taught and what pedagogy and assessment methods are employed across all grades and subject within the school curriculum.

Teaching language and literature starts in Grade 1, which corresponds to the age of 7, and continues throughout all stages of compulsory education, from primary to middle to upper secondary schools. The goal of language education is defined as “to develop students’ literacy, language proficiency and interaction skills, and guide them towards developing an interest in language, literature and other forms of culture and gaining awareness of themselves as communicators and language users” (Finnish National Board of Education, 2016: 185). Key content area in language and literature education are acting in interactive situations, interpreting texts, producing texts and understanding language, literature and culture.

Skills related to interpreting literary texts are developed gradually as part of the language development. Even at the primary school level, students start developing complex text comprehension and interpretation skills through exposure to different types of texts. In Grades 1-2, students are introduced to different types of texts, including children’s literature, start learning and practicing text comprehension strategies and interpreting texts with a focus on the meaning and structures of the texts, and reflect on ways of expression and play with the language. Students

also get to know the library and its use, with reading encouraged as pastime. In Grades 3-6, the focus is on examining the features of language and elements of literature while interpreting and producing texts. Students progress from shorter texts to entire books. At this level, students are expected to be able to compare diverse texts, looking at intertextuality, and use concepts of the narrator, the topic and the theme to interpret texts. They also should explore how the authors vary the language according to the situation and the topic.

With the shift to the next stage in compulsory schooling (Grades 7-9), the focus of language and literature classes shifts to promoting students' linguistic and cultural skills in diverse communication environments. With this objective in mind, students are guided to develop both text comprehension and interpretation strategies and metacognitive skills. Students should be able to recognise and interpret metaphors and symbols in a text, analyse its linguistic and narrative features, including register and style and the impact of the linguistic choices on the style and the tone of a text.

At the end of Grade 9, students are expected not only to be thoughtful readers, but also producers who can express their thoughts in writing through diverse types of texts, choosing appropriate ways of expression. They are also encouraged to apply metacognitive strategies to their writing process, assess themselves as writers and improve through feedback.

The curriculum does not prescribe specific texts that students need to study. Using National Core Curriculum as a guide, teachers are free to choose texts that they think best suit the needs, interests and demands of their classes. Also, Finland does not have a centralized textbook production or inspection system: commercial publishers produce textbooks, from which teachers are free to choose or produce and use their own materials, which is in line with the policy of school autonomy and trust in teachers as responsible professionals.

Lack of curriculum clarity and coherence: lessons from Uzbekistan

In contrast to Finland, Uzbekistan's first-time participation in PISA-2022, with majority of 15-year-old students demonstrating lack of basic literacy skills, revealed a number of problems that need to be addressed. More than 60% of Uzbekistani students failed to reach the minimum proficiency level in any of three literacy areas tested. Also, there were no high performers – those who reached literacy levels 5 and 6 (NRI named after Avloniy, 2023). These results are in line with a number of studies conducted earlier, such as PIRLS or EGRA, that revealed that schoolchildren in Uzbekistan have serious problems in understanding what they read (Gazeta.uz, 2019; Harden et al, 2022; Mullis et al, 2023).

Uzbekistan's Law on Education states that the aims of education are: in primary education (Grades 1-4) – to develop students' basic literacy skills and provide them with the knowledge, skills and competences needed for secondary education, in basic secondary education (Grades 5-9) – to provide students with the necessary volume of knowledge, skills and competences as well as to develop independent thinking and analytical skills, and in upper secondary education (Grades 10-11) – to provide students with the necessary volume of knowledge, skills and competences and to teach jobs that do not require high level of qualification (Law on Education, 2020).

The goals of education, both in terms of soft skills and subject-specific competences, remain largely unclear. This is because the State Educational Standards (Curriculum) approved by the government of Uzbekistan in 2017 was discontinued with the shift from 12-year compulsory education (so called "9+3" system, in which students spent nine years in schools and three more years either in academic lyceums, which aimed to prepare students to tertiary education and offered

in-depth study of selected subject areas, or in vocational colleges for those students who wanted to learn a profession and join workforce after compulsory education) to 11-year compulsory education with most students remaining in general schools until the end of Grade 11. In 2020, Ministry of Public Education (as it was called then) initiated the National Curriculum project, which would shift the focus of education from memorization of theoretical knowledge to the development of 21st century skills, including cognitive skills, critical and creative thinking and multiliteracy (Gazeta.uz, 2021). UNICEF, whose analysis of then existing school curriculum in 2018 revealed that it focused too much on imparting knowledge rather than enhancing skills to learn and apply knowledge, supported the curriculum reform initiative and provided technical support to develop National Curriculum Framework with a focus on competency-based approach (UNICEF Uzbekistan, 2021). This transition to the new curriculum was to be completed by 2025, but in 2023, it was halted with no explanations from the authorities and later, officials from the Ministry of Pre-School and School Education (the new name for the ministry overseeing compulsory education, after the merge of Ministries of Pre-School Education and Public Education) announced that the draft of a new curriculum of compulsory education will be published for public discussion by 2025 (Gazeta.uz, 2024).

Thus, no authoritative documents that specify goals and objectives for the whole system of compulsory education or for specific subjects taught in schools seem to be in effect. The documents that teachers can currently rely on in their teaching are basic education plan, which is basically a table that shows allocation of hours for different subjects across all grades, and so-called “calendar-thematic plans” for each subject, which is another table that list sequence of topics to be covered in lessons, with no learning objectives. Given the centralised, single-textbook policy that currently operates in Uzbekistan, with all teachers having to use the same textbooks published by or endorsed by the ministry (Ministry of Public Education and UNICEF Uzbekistan, 2020), the contents of these ministry-mandated textbooks become de-facto curriculum.

Although students start reading literary texts as early as in Grade 1, within the framework of “Nature Language” and “Reading” lessons, literature as a subject on its own is introduced when students transition from primary to secondary school (Grade 5). Interestingly, Grades 5, 8, 9 and 11 use textbooks published in or before 2017, which are based on the discontinued curricula of 2017 and backwards, while Grades 6, 7 and 10 use textbooks published in 2022 and based on National Curriculum Framework on Literature, developed in 2020-21 in cooperation with UNICEF. A closer look at pedagogy and structure of these textbook may give an idea of differences between the curricula they are based on. Thus, textbooks based on the discontinued curriculum of 2017 or its earlier version, place a lot of emphasis on learning facts about writers and their writings. They contain lengthy passages that provide information on the lives of authors whose works are being studied and ready analyses of their texts supplied by textbook authors, which may discourage students from putting efforts to come up with their own interpretations of literary texts. Questions and tasks that follow each chapter also require students mostly to reproduce information rather than engaging with the texts, creating their own interpretations or producing original works based on or inspired from the texts. Most tasks are individual, with very few, if any, tasks that require student collaboration.

Textbooks based on National Curriculum Framework seem to take a different approach. They employ a three-stage approach to working with a text. Pre-reading tasks aim to activate prior knowledge, raise motivation to read the text and prepare students to understand the text by

providing the context. While-reading questions require students to work closer with the text, paying attention to the language, literary devices, characters, plot and cause-effect relationships. Post-reading tasks help students to create their own interpretations of the text, evaluate it and extend it by producing, either individually or in groups, analytical or creative works based on the text. Information about the lives of authors is kept to minimum and no ready-made analyses of texts are provided. This approach seems to be inspired by reader-response theory and view of reading as an active, two-way, transaction process (Rosenblatt, 1982).

Texts included into literature textbooks contain examples of different genres (narrative stories, lyric, drama, epic stories) from different periods and authors. Probably understandingly, more emphasis is given to local (Uzbek) authors than world literature, the latter being represented by some renowned names, such as Homer, Cervantes, Shakespeare, Tagore, Remarque and Hemingway and some lesser-known authors, such as Gianni Rodari or Nodar Dumbadze. Due to a single-textbook policy and requirement from the ministry to follow the same “calendar-thematic plans” (see above), teachers cannot change texts.

Conclusions

Although knowing what successful education systems do or have done to achieve the results they have may not provide other systems with a ready-to-use recipes, analysing the experience and features of top-performing, resilient systems will help policy makers and educators to make inferences, draw lessons and adapt these lessons to their own situations (Schleicher, 2018). Thus, given the current position of Uzbekistan in terms of education and its ambitious goal to be among top-30 PISA nations by 2030 (President of Uzbekistan, 2019), it seems worthwhile to compare Uzbekistan’s approaches to education in general and to literature education in particular, and compare these approaches to practices that proved more successful internationally. Thus, if students are to develop reading literacy and be more engaged, thoughtful, critical readers, literature curriculum, regardless of whether it is taught as a separate subject or part of language curriculum, needs to be well aligned with clearly articulated general goals of education and yet set specific subject-related objectives which give both teachers and students a clear vision of where to head for.

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